

Irish Research eLibrary

National Open Access Monitor Survey: Organisational Identity: New Submissions

IMPORTANT

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The first iteration of this survey was originally run during October 2023.

If your organisation has already submitted to that survey, **DO NOT COMPLETE THIS SURVEY AGAIN.**

Only complete this form if this is the first time your organisation will be submitting a survey response.

If you would like to update an existing submission, please complete a change file submission here: [\[link\]](#).

Any submission from an organisation that has already submitted will not be actioned.

If you would like to check if your organisation has already submitted, please check here: [\[download link\]](#)

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Introduction

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Introduction

This survey is carried out under the National Open Access Monitoring project, funded by Ireland's National Open Research Forum (NORF) under the NORF Open Research Fund 2022 to address one of the six priority actions of Ireland's [National Action Plan for Open Research 2022-2023](#).

This survey is for Research Performing Organisations, Research Funding Organisations and Publisher stakeholders of the National Open Access Monitor.

The purpose of this survey is to empower stakeholders to self-identify how their entities will be represented in the National Open Access Monitor.

The survey expects one response from each stakeholder entity. If multiple responses are obtained and inconsistencies occur, the Project Manager will follow up directly with respondents to clarify. To view a reference PDF of this survey, please click here [\[link\]](#).

Throughout this survey:

- The National Open Access Monitor, Ireland will be referred to as the Monitor.
- Research Performing Organisations will be referred to as RPOs and Research Funding Organisation will be referred to as RFOs.
- Persistent Identifiers will be referred to as PIDs.

The sections of this survey are:

1. Consent
2. Survey Respondent Identification
3. Potential Survey Skip Point [for Publishers]
4. RPO and RFO Dashboards
5. RPO and RFO Identification
6. RPO and RFO Categorisation
7. Publicly Funded Organisations/Entities
8. Affiliated Organisations/Entities
9. Persistent Identifiers (PIDs): RPOs and RFOs Publisher Branching [end survey for non-Publishers]
10. RPO/RFO Publisher Identification
11. Persistent Identifiers (PIDs): RPO/RFO Publishers
12. Publisher Identification
13. Persistent Identifiers (PIDs): Publishers
14. Optional: RPO Identity Supplement
15. Submit Survey

There is no deadline for responses to this survey.

Please note: all survey data will be retained and hosted on a third party (Online Surveys) server and not on a MU server. For more information on how and why this survey data is being collected, and how it will be managed, please refer to the [Stakeholder Information Sheet and Consent Form](#).

Your submission may be paused at any time by pressing "Finish Later". Respondents who click on the "Finish Later" link are taken to a page giving the survey's closing date and a 'finish later' URL. This URL can be used to return to the survey at the page on which you clicked the 'Finish later' link. The URL can be either bookmarked in your browser, or you will be asked if you would like the URL to be emailed to you.

A download of your responses will be available to you on completion.

If you decide to take part, you are still free to withdraw at any time without giving a reason and/or to withdraw your information up until such time as the contributions are actioned upon for the development of the National Open Access Monitor. The deadline to withdraw a submission from this form is COB the Thursday after your submission (in the case of Thursday submissions, the deadline is COB that same day).

If you have any questions relating to this survey, or require assistance in filling it out, please contact Dr Catherine Ferris (National Open Access Monitor Project Manager): catherine.ferris@mu.ie

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Consent

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Formal contributors to the National Open Access Monitor Project (e.g. through stakeholder surveys like this) are required to complete and return a consent form **in advance of contributing**. This is a requirement of the Maynooth University Research Ethics Procedure.

If you have not yet completed a consent form:

1. stop here
2. complete the consent form, available at [this link](#)
3. return it to catherine.ferris@mu.ie
4. and then return to this survey.

Important: if the date/time of the survey response precedes the date/time that the consent form is received, the survey response will be **immediately deleted**.

If you have completed the consent form (an image of the first page is below as a reminder), please select yes below and continue.

Purpose of the Study. I am Dr Catherine Ferris, [JReL](#) Open Scholarship Officer (Maynooth University) and Project Manager of the National Open Access Monitor Project, funded by the National Open Research Forum.

This project will develop a monitor for open access at the national level, initially through pilot reports and a national dashboard to publish, analyse and track progress towards 100% open access. The key objectives and expected outcomes are to:

- Work to arrive at a community-agreed definition for Open Access at the national level
- Build on previous NORF work, engaging with national stakeholders (DFHERIS, NORF, NORF 2022 Open Research Fund projects, HEA, research funding organisation, research performing organisations, national research infrastructures, publishers etc.) to gather and validate user requirements for Open Access monitoring
- Work with external vendors to deliver reports and a national dashboard to help Ireland publish, analyse and track open access rates at the national level.
- Document challenges that should be addressed in long-term monitoring solutions and recommend steps to be taken, including workflows for data validation and enrichment.
- Work to improve the quality and depth of data used for the national dashboard in line with international best practice through stakeholder collaboration with institutions, funders etc. and direct input or validation where possible.
- Following NORF and Science Europe recommendations, ensure that the monitor uses data and bibliographic databases that are openly accessible, is built using open infrastructure, and is publicly accessible to view and analyse.

A copy of the Project Plan is available here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7331432>

What will the study involve and what information will be collected?

Participants will be asked to provide input and contribute as representatives of stakeholder entities, over the course of the two-year project (1 November 2022-1 November 2024), in the following areas:

- to arrive at a community-agreed definition for Open Access in this context at the national level
- to validate, and if required expand on, the user stories and functional requirements of the National Open Access Monitor identified by the NORF OA Monitoring Policy Brief Group. These functional requirements should explicitly state current OA reporting metrics for each stakeholder, required data points and potential future requirements.
- to monitor and track the costs associated with contributing to this project and to provide this data to the Project Manager, for inclusion in the final report to the funder, in a pseudonymised format (to the high-level stakeholder group) to demonstrate the cost of this work to the national research system.
- to provide metadata and persistent identifiers as required, to enable the successful delivery of the pilot dashboard
- to provide feedback on the pilot dashboard
- if necessary, to work with the Project Manager to determine the impact of vendor non-deliverables
- to work with the Project Manager to identify gaps, incomplete representation, or errors in pilot data.
- to work to improve the quality and depth of data used for the national dashboard.

1. Have you completed the National Open Access Monitor Project Stakeholder Consent Form, and returned it to catherine.ferris@mu.ie? *

Yes

No

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Consent Disclaimer

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The National Open Access Monitor Project Stakeholder Consent Form allows participants to choose to be pseudonymised, if you would rather your contribution was not publicly attributed to you and your organisation/entity.

However, due to the nature and purpose of this survey on Organisational Identity, the **identity of your organisation/entity cannot be pseudonymised**. Therefore, while your name will remain pseudonymised, it will be evident that a representative of your organisation/entity contributed to this survey.

- If you chose pseudonymisation in the consent form, and are happy to continue with this survey under these conditions, please continue.
- If you chose pseudonymisation in the consent form, and are **not** happy to continue with this survey under these conditions, please stop here and forward this survey onto another person in your organisation/entity to complete.

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Survey Respondent Identification

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2. Your name *

3. Your department *

4. Your job title *

5. Your email address (the Project Manager may need to follow-up with you on your responses. Your email address will not be made public.) *

6. The name of the organisation/entity that you represent *

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Potential Survey Skip Point

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7. Questions 8-30 are applicable for RPOs and RFOs only, and are not applicable to Publishers. If your organisation/entity is a Publisher (and not also an RPO/RFO), then please indicate below and the survey will skip directly to the Publisher Persistent Identifier section of the survey *

- My organisation/entity is a Publisher
- My organisation/entity is an RPO; an RFO; an RPO & RFO; an RPO & Publisher; an RFO & Publisher; or an RPO, RFO & Publisher

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Publisher Identification

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35. Please indicate the full name of your Publisher organisation/entity, to be associated with the persistent identifiers that you will provide in the next section *

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Persistent Identifiers (PIDs): Publishers

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The [tender](#) requirements for the Monitor specified that the vendor must (at a minimum) use PIDs to identify Irish scholarly publications:

M6	The Monitor MUST , at a minimum:	Compliant (Yes / No)	Insert Comment
	<ul style="list-style-type: none">Use the Budapest Open Access Initiative definition of "open access": "By "open access" to this literature, we mean its free availability on the public internet, permitting any users to read, download, copy, distribute, print, search, or link to the full texts of these articles, crawl them for indexing, pass them as data to software, or use them for any other lawful purpose, without financial, legal, or technical barriers other than those inseparable from gaining access to the internet itself." https://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read/Use the Unpaywall definition of "open access types".Initially focus on monitoring peer-reviewed articles and conference proceedingsHave the potential in the future to expand to monitor monographs, book chapters, other scholarly publication outputs, open research activities and measures (to be defined during Action 6.2.3, expected in 2025-2027)Focus on publications which can be uniquely and unambiguously identified by a DOI.Define an "Irish scholarly publication" as a publication which contains the unique persistent identifier of an Irish organisation in the publication and/or the publication metadata and/or the persistent identifier metadata.		

The Monitor will be built using open data from the OpenAIRE Graph:

DATA BACKBONE: THE OPENAIRE GRAPH

- **A Scientific Knowledge Graph**
 - Timely and comprehensive coverage of research outputs
 - 129K data sources, 3M projects, and 235M research outputs (publications, software, datasets, other research products)
 - Near monthly updates
- **Precision, depth & processing**
 - Rigorous cleaning, deduplication, and enrichment for optimal accuracy
 - Enriched metadata links: Research results to projects, author affiliations, and classifications (FoS, SDG)
 - Techniques for duplicate identification in addition to OpenAIRE's curation tools
- **Robustness & openness**
 - Maintenance, load balancing, backups, overseen by the OpenAIRE technology centre
 - Open data & transparent methodologies

This section is to capture the PIDs that represent Publishers that will be represented in the Monitor, to enable OpenAIRE to query the OpenAIRE graph using those PIDs and identify research outputs associated with your Publisher organisation/entity.

Please supply the most comprehensive listing of identifiers that you have available to you. When providing lists, please provide the PIDs separated by semicolons (no spaces) (e.g. 8798;8849)

If your Publisher organisation is part of another organisation/entity, please only supply the PIDs that identify your discreet **Publisher** organisation/entity.

36. ROR

<https://ror.org/>

37. RINGGOLD

<https://www.copyright.com/solutions-ringgold/guest-users/>

38. GRID

https://digitalscience.figshare.com/articles/dataset/GRID_release_2021-09-16/16685428?backTo=/collections/GRID/3812929

39. ISNI

<https://isni.oclc.org/cbs/>

40. ISSNs

<https://portal.issn.org/>

41. e-ISSNs

<https://portal.issn.org/>

42. ISSN-L

<https://portal.issn.org/>

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43. Please select Continue and follow
the instructions to complete the survey *

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Submit

Please click submit below to complete the survey

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[Submit](#)

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